

Supplementary Figures

a.

b.

Supplementary Figure S1 : Distribution of SNP-based C_2 values (contrast statistic) computed with the program BAYPASS. a. Focal Test ; b. Control Test. Black lines indicate the empirical probability density functions and magenta dotted lines indicate the expected Chi-squared probability density functions with one degree of freedom.

p-value: 0.6633
Z-score: -0.379
n perm: 10000
randomization: resampleRegions

Supplementary Figure S2: Results of permutation tests assessing whether outlier genes are overrepresented in coldspots of recombination (as reported by Morgan et al. 2017). 10,000 permutations were conducted.

a.

b.

Supplementary Figure S3: Results of two permutation tests assessing (a) whether outlier genes are over-represented in genomic regions identified as candidates for hybrid sterility [1,2]; (b) whether outlier genes are closer or more distant to candidate hybrid sterility regions than expected by chance. 10,000 permutations were conducted for each test.

a.

Chromosome 1

b.

Chromosome 7

c.

Chromosome 19

Supplementary Figure S4 : Autocorrelation (ACF, left panels) and partial autocorrelation (partial ACF, right panels) estimates in genetic differentiation (BAYPASS C_2 contrast statistic), measured in 10-kb, 50-kb and 100-kb windows. Results are shown for three chromosomes: (a) chromosome 1 (the longest), (b) chromosome 7 (containing several clusters of outlier genes) and (c) chromosome 19 (the shortest). The auto-correlation at lag 0 is by definition equal to 1. Dashed lines represent the 95% CIs around an autocorrelation coefficient equal to zero.

Supplementary Figure S5: Local score distribution along the autosomes and the X chromosome. The local score is computed as the Lindley process based on the score function $-\log_{10}(p_{\text{FLK}}) - 1$ (Fariello et al 2017). Positions are indicated in Mb. Grey plain and dotted horizontal lines indicate respectively the thresholds corresponding to the top 5% and the top 1% local score measures, computed for each chromosome. Grey dotted vertical lines indicate the centre of the region detected by the local score approach.

Supplementary Figure S6 : Results of a parameter-free test for homogeneous distribution of outlier genes in the genome. Bars indicate the permutation null distribution; the blue vertical line indicates the observed average number of outlier genes per 500 kb windows. 50,000 permutations were conducted.

Supplementary Figure S7: Details of Figure 3 for the three main gene clusters on chromosomes 2, 7 and 9. The three shown tracks are (top) position and local scores for significant local score regions (green lines), (middle) position and C_2_max values for C_2_max outlier genes and (bottom) position and C_2_mean values for C_2_mean outlier genes. For C_2 outlier genes, *Vmn* are in blue, *Olfr* in purple, and any other type of outlier genes in light green.